

Outcomes of Bi-Columnar Plating in the Treatment of Proximal Tibia Fractures: A Focus on Schatzker Types V and VI

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Abstract:

Introduction: Controversy still surrounds the fixation of comminuted bicondylar tibial plateau fractures. Several fixation methods could be used for tibial plateau fractures. All of these techniques have strengths and weaknesses and there is no clear consensus on which leads to the best outcomes. We describe the effectiveness of Bicolumnar plating for proximal tibia fractures of Schatzker type V and VI

Materials & Methods: This is a prospective study conducted with proximal tibial fractures: Schatzker type V & type VI. All patients underwent bicolumnar plating of proximal tibia. All patients were postoperatively assessed for functional outcome using the Knee Society Score and radiological outcomes by Modified Rasmussen scoring criteria.

Results: 21 Cases were operated with mean age of 43 years. The mean time for fracture union was 4 months (16 weeks). The mean knee flexion in this study group was 120.67 degrees. 17 patients had excellent functional and objective knee score and 4 patients had good functional and objective knee score. None of the patients had fair or bad scoring

Discussion: A double incision Double plating technique is recommended by the Association for Osteosynthesis/Association for the Study of Internal Fixation for the treatment of complex tibial plateau fractures. . In our study, all fractures united within expected time with average time of 15-16 weeks. In our series, mean flexion at the knee joint was 120.67 degrees. But our follow up duration was only of 2 years and long term follow up of at least 6-8 years is required for diagnosis of secondary osteoarthritis. . Age, fracture union, objective and functional knee society score outcome have an effect on final radiological outcome. Lesser the age of patient, better is the radiological outcome.

Conclusion: Medial and lateral plate stabilization of comminuted bicondylar tibial plateau fractures through medial and lateral surgical approaches is a superior treatment method; however, residual dysfunction is common.

Keywords: Proximal Tibia Fractures, Bicolumnar Plating.

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Introduction

Tibial plateau fractures can range from a simple lateral split pattern to very complex bi-condylar injuries that can be a source of great disability. When part of the articular surface becomes depressed, the articular surface becomes incongruous and a smaller portion of the joint comes to bear all the weight, which increases the stress borne by the articular cartilage [1].

Tibial plateau fractures are generally classified according to the method developed by Schatzker. Schatzker type V and VI fractures are high-energy fractures. Several fixation methods could be used for tibial plateau fractures including uni-column fixation, bi-columnar plating with single or dual incision, a hybrid external fixator or a Less Invasive Stabilizing System (LISS). All of these techniques have strengths and weaknesses and

there is no clear consensus on which leads to the best outcomes [2]. We studied the usefulness of bi-columnar fixation with dual incision approach among patients with Schatzker type V and VI tibial plateau fractures.

Materials & Methodology

Aim: Impact of Bi-Columnar Plating on the Functional and Radiological Recovery of Schatzker Type V and VI Proximal Tibia Fractures.

This is a prospective study conducted from a medical college in India during the period April 2014 and March 2016. We included proximal tibial fractures: Schatzker type V & type VI and excluded proximal tibia fractures of other types, open fractures, Fractures with compartment syndrome and cases having associated fractures. A total of 21

patients, of complex high-energy proximal tibia fractures classified as Schatzker type V and VI tibial plateau fractures who underwent bi-columnar plating were included in this longitudinal study after obtaining informed consent from patients and approval from the ethics committee. All patients were postoperatively assessed for functional outcome using the Knee Society Score and radiological outcomes by Modified Rasmussen scoring criteria.

Pre-operative evaluation: Preoperatively the patients were evaluated clinically and radiologically which included antero-posterior, lateral, medial oblique and lateral oblique xrays of the affected knee. Computerized Tomographic evaluation was done in cases which had more comminution and when x-rays was inconclusive and MRI was done in suspected ligamentous and soft tissue injuries. All of the cases in this study were treated operatively as articular surface reconstruction was the main consideration. Injured limb was splinted with a plaster slab or knee immobilizer pre-operatively. The patients were operated for surgery as soon as possible depending on their medical condition, skin condition around fracture and the amount of swelling. All surgeries were done under C-arm image intensifier control.

Surgical Procedure: On the day of surgery, in the theatre skin preparation done using chlorhexidine solution. Prophylactic antibiotic (third generation cephalosporin) is given 30 minutes prior to skin incision.

Epidural and Spinal anesthesia was used for all cases.

Patients were placed on a radiolucent table in supine position with a sand bag under ipsilateral gluteal region for the anterolateral approach. If posteromedial approach is planned, sand bag was placed on contralateral hip. All patients were operated with tourniquet inflated during surgeries.

An antero-lateral approach was used for visualisation of the lateral fragment, reduction and fixation with a lateral column plate. Anterolateral approach for proximal tibia was done by a curvilinear longitudinal incision starting from the lateral femoral epicondyle and curving over the Gerdy's tubercle and parallel and lateral to tibial shin. The iliotibial band was elevated from the Gerdy's tubercle. The tibialis anterior muscle was elevated subperiosteally to reach to lateral tibial condyle and shaft. Anatomical lateral locking plates were fixed on lateral surface and sometimes "L" buttress plate was used. Closure was done over suction drain.

The medial or the posteromedial fragment was exposed subperiosteally by elevating the pesanserinus. Once the medial fragment was

reduced, a small buttress plate was placed beneath the pes anserinus. Small stab incisions were used to fix the plate to the bone. Only if the fragment was posterior, open posteromedial approach was used. The posteromedial fragment was exposed by retracting pesanserinus tendons anteriorly and the medial head of the gastrocnemius laterally. Adequate visualization of fragments was done to aid in anatomical reduction. Anteromedial portion of tibia which is subcutaneous was not disturbed. Reduction of fragment was confirmed on image intensifier and fixed with a plate. We used locking/non-locking proximal tibia plate for fixation of the fragments.

Post-operative care and rehabilitation

Antibiotics: The patient was given IIIrd generation cephalosporins for the first 2 days and then followed by oral antibiotics for 3 days.

Analgesics: Until 2nd post-operative day pain was managed with epidural analgesic pump infusion, and was removed on 2nd post-operative day. There after parental analgesics were given.

Post-operative care: The patient is nursed in absolute aseptic conditions in the postoperative ward with the limb protected with elevation pillow or an extension knee brace in cases of instability. Drains were removed at the end of 48 hrs.

Rehabilitation protocol

- This actually begins postoperatively as soon as pain subsides.
- Active ankle dorsiflexion and plantar flexion, quadriceps and gluteal exercises are started. Upper limb and breathing exercises were also done.
- Radiographs were assessed for adequacy of articular reduction, metaphysio-diaphyseal reduction, and alignment. If instability present or tibial tuberosity fracture was present then postoperatively hinged knee brace was given.
- Non weight-bearing walking and static quadriceps strengthening exercises were started on the 1st Postoperative Day (POD) itself. Patients were allowed to sit in bed on first post-operative day. After drain removal patient was made to stand and walk. Patient was mobilized with protected weight bearing for first 3 weeks. Patient was mobilized with full weight bearing after 3 weeks. Sutures were removed on the 12th post-operative day.
- Patients were reviewed at 1 month, 3 month and 6 month intervals and assessment of fracture healing and knee joint range of motion for a minimum of 6 months.
- All the patients who satisfied the selection criteria were called for follow up at the end of the study period. Radiographs of the knee and leg in supine position were obtained in the an-

teroposterior (AP) and lateral planes to assess the articular congruity, the metaphyseodiaphyseal alignment, for any evidence of new arthritic changes.

- The patients were also questioned regarding functional recovery and their responses noted. The results were analyzed according to the knee society scoring criteria.

Radiological outcome of the fracture fixation by studying Modified Rasmussen scoring criteria.

Follow-up

Follow-up was done at 2 weeks and then followed at 1 month, 3 months and 6 months. At the time of follow-up, clinical features like surgical scar, range of movements, presence of pain, instability was observed. Various radiological features like callus formation or healing, maintenance of fracture reduction, widening and depression of articular surfaces, varus and valgus collapse, signs of secondary osteoarthritis were observed.

Bony union

Was defined as union of at least 3 cortices in Antero-posterior and Lateral views on follow-up radiographs. Nonunion was defined as absence of any signs of union at 6 months after surgery.

Malalignment

Malalignment of the proximal tibia was determined by measuring the tibial plateau angle (the medial angle between the tangential line and anatomic axial of the tibia) on antero-posterior radiographs and the posterior slope angle (the angle between the tangential line of medial plateau and the perpendicular line of the anterior tibial cortex) on lateral radiographs; tibial plateau angle 90° or 80° or posterior slope angle 15° or -5° was considered indicative of malalignment. Secondary loss of reduction was defined as an increase of 2mm of intra-articular step-off, and secondary loss of alignment was defined as an increase of 3°

malalignment when compared with the first postoperative radiograph.

Results:

21 Cases were operated with mean age of 43 years, out of which 15 patient's sustained injury on the left side and 6 on the right side. All the fractures in this study were classified according to Schatzker's classification system with Type V – 10 (48%) & Type VI – 11 (52%). Out of the 21 patients that underwent surgery in the study, patients who were treated with lateral and medial column were 11 (52%) in total and patients who were treated with lateral and postero-medial column were 10 (48%) in total.

BONY Union: Bony union was seen in some cases as low as 3 months (12 weeks) and in some cases as high as 5 months (20 weeks). The mean time for fracture union was 4 months (16 weeks) [Tab 1].

The mean knee flexion in this study group was 120.67 degrees [Tab2] At 6months follow-up pain can be caused due to a lot of factors ranging from incongruity, instability or secondary osteoarthritis to trauma.

Patients at the end of six months were followed up for pain in our study, 16 (76.1%) cases were pain-free. 4 (19.0%) cases had occasional pain (Due to instability). 1 (4.7%) case had moderate pain. In this study group, 1 (4.7%) case with flexion contracture of 20 degrees was observed.

Schatzker type VI, varus malunion and non-compliance of the patient with respect to non-adherence of weight bearing protocols and lack of physiotherapy was probably the reason to development of flexion contracture.

One case of type VI in which ORIF with plating and screws was done, developed varus malunion with stiffness at knee with range of motion 10-90 degree, due to lack of compliance and early weight bearing . There was no case of non-union.

Table 1: Objective knee score

Score	No. Of patients
Excellent (80-100)	17 (80.9%)
Good (70-79)	4 (19.1%)
Fair (60-69)	0
Poor (<60)	0
Total	21 (100%)

Table 2: Functional knee score

Score	No. Of patients
Excellent (80-100)	17 (80.9%)
Good (70-79)	4 (19.1%)
Fair (60-69)	0
Poor (<60)	0
Total	21 (100%)

Table 3: Radiological outcome by Modified Rasmussen scoring criteria.

Score	No. Of patients
Excellent (28-30)	6 (28.5%)
Good (24-27)	13 (61.9%)
Fair (20-23)	2 (9.5%)
Poor (<20)	0
Total	21 (100%)

Figure 1: Bony union

Figure 2: Mean flexion of the knee

Discussion

The most common difficulties are faced by the surgeon while dealing with intra-articular proximal tibial fractures are the compromised skin and soft tissue envelope, which invites a high rate of complications following attempted open reduction and internal fixation, and poor bone quality and comminuted fracture patterns creating difficulty in achieving stable fixation [3,4]. Complex tibial plateau fractures still remain a challenge to most Orthopedic surgeons. Historically single incision technique for dual plating had high incidence of wound break-down and infection [5]. With the advent of isolated lateral plating with locking compression plate the spectrum has shifted towards locking plate with medial fragment being stabilized by screws passed through lateral plate. Varus collapse in these patients raised the question of its sustainability and the reason found to be inadequate fixation of posteromedial fragment. This has paved way for dual plating via two incision technique [6,7]. A double incision Double plating technique is recommended by the Association for Osteosynthesis/Association for the Study of Internal Fixation for the treatment of complex tibial plateau fractures [4]. In our study, the tibial plateau fractures were due to RTA and between the age group 26 to 65 years (mean age 43.33 years). Out of 21 patients, 15 (71%) were males and 6 (29%) were females. All fractures were high velocity road traffic accidents. Type V were 11 patients (52%) and type VI were 10 patients (48%) and there was a left sided predominance (71%), compared to right side (29%). Patients were immobilized with above knee POP slab (12 patients: 57.1%), extension knee brace (5 patients: 23.8%) or a knee spanning external fixator (4 patients : 19%). Patients were operated between 4 to 14 days on an average of 6.5 days. Patients treated with lateral and medial column were 11 in total and patients who were treated with lateral and posteromedial column were 10 in total.

Bony union

Bony union of these high velocity trauma is influenced by a number of factors. Age of the patient, physical and nutritional condition, extent of soft tissue injury, surgical exposure, handling of soft tissue, adequate fixation and rehabilitation have an impact on the outcome of bony union. In our study, all fractures united within expected time with average time of 15-16 weeks. Various other authors like Zhang et al., showed an average of 14.1 weeks in the double buttress plate group and 13.7 weeks in the combination plate group [8]. Prasad et al., found that union occurred in 8-22 weeks (average 14 weeks) [9]. None of the patient's received bone grafting, as the metaphyseal region is richer in vascular supply and cancellous bone heals much better due to this fact. A dual

column plating helps in aiding maintenance and protects this region thereby not resulting in secondary malreduction and mal-alignment. It is important to note that pre-operative, per-operative and post-operative management of soft tissue is absolute vital to preservation of blood supply which is key in union of the bone.

Mean flexion

Flexion of the knee joint in these injuries directly correlates to the objective and functional outcome of the surgery. Type V and Type VI injuries are most common types of proximal tibia injuries that tend to cause reduced flexion of the knee joint due to multitude of reasons. Fracture pattern, prolonged pre-operative immobilisation of the knee with POP or external fixator, quadriceps wasting and delay in post-operative rehabilitative measures, all have an impact on the outcome. In our series, mean flexion at the knee joint was 120.67 degrees. Yong et al with a mean flexion of 121.2 degrees [10]. In our study, 1 (4.7%) case with flexion contracture of 20 degrees was observed. Schatzker type VI, varus malunion and non-compliance of the patient with respect to non-adherence of weight bearing protocols and lack of physiotherapy was probably the reason to development of flexion contracture. 2 (9.5%) cases had superficial infection, one at 3 months and another at 6 months, of which both resolved by antibiotics. 1 (4.7%) case of type VI in which ORIF with plating and screws was done, developed varus malunion with stiffness at knee with range of motion 10-90 degree, due to lack of compliance and early weight bearing . There was no case of non-union.

Yu et al., showed knee stiffness in 9 cases, 3 cases of varus deformity, 2 cases of valgus deformity, 2 cases of wound infection (for which debridement of wound followed by external fixation were performed after implants removal), 10 cases of post-traumatic osteoarthritis of knee (for which 2 patients were operated for total knee arthroplasty at a duration of 1 year and 2 years postoperatively, and remaining 8 were followed up regularly without any need for operative procedure during the follow up periods) and 1 case of delayed union [11]. Oh et al., concluded by showing the complications like 1 cm shortening in 1 case and mild malalignments in 2 cases (varus of less than 10°). One case of superficial infection healed after removal of the plate. No cases of deep infections were seen [12]. Barei et al., showed deep wound infections in 7 cases (8.4%), out of which 3 were associated with septic arthritis (3.6%). Clinical resolution occurred only after an average of at least 3 additional procedures. In a patient with dysvascular limb requiring urgent vascular reconstruction was associated with a deep wound infection. Thirteen patients who required secondary procedure for complication include implant

removal secondary to local discomfort, 5 patients requiring knee manipulation, 2 patients operated for excision of heterotopic ossification in order to improve knee motion, 1 patient operated for an equinus contracture release, and 1 patient operated for a metadiaphyseal nonunion. There were 16 patients (19.3%) with deep venous thromboses. No patient developed pulmonary embolism [13]. But our follow up duration was only of 2 years and long term follow up of at least 6-8 years is required for diagnosis of secondary osteoarthritis.

Associated injuries, fracture union, objective knee society score and radiological outcome have an effect on functional outcome. Associated injuries if present have good functional outcome, whereas if absent have excellent functional outcome. Earlier the fracture union, excellent is the result, whereas slight delay in fracture union will have good result. Better the objective knee score, excellent is the result. Better the MRA radiological score, excellent is the result. Age, fracture union, objective and functional knee society score outcome have an effect on final radiological outcome. Lesser the age of patient, better is the radiological outcome.

Conclusion

Medial and lateral plate stabilization of comminuted bicondylar tibial plateau fractures through medial and lateral surgical approaches is a superior treatment method; however, residual dysfunction is common. In about half of our patients, an accurate articular reduction was possible and was associated with better outcomes within the confines of the injury severity.

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